

FIZIKADA GARMONIK TEBRANISHLARNI HARAKAT QONUNLARINI MATEMATIK USULDA ISBOTLASH VA ANIQLASH

B. Xusanov

SamDAQU dotsent, bozorboyxusanov98@gmail.com

G'.Yu.Nodirov

SamDAQU dotsent v.b., nodirovgulom75@gmail.com

U.A.Nishanov

SamDAQU o'qituvchi, nishonov807@gmail.com

J.M.Parmonov

SamDAQU o'qituvchi, jamshiparmanov1987@gmail.com

M.A.Vaxobov

SamDAQU o'qituvchi, vahobovmehroj62@gmail.com

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Annotatsiya. Garmonik tebranishlarni harakat qonunlari yoki harakat tenglamalarini hosil qilishda «Oliy matematika» fanining ikkinchi tartibli o'zgarmas koeffitsientli chiziqli tenglamalarini yechimlarini topish usulidan foydalanib topilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: garmonik, tebranishlar, massa, prujina, reaksiya kuchi, statik uzayish, tenglama, bikrlilik, ostsilyator, amplituda, chastota, faza, davr.

Aytmalik og'irligi R bo'lgan yuk tinch turgan holatdagi uzunligi l bo'lgan vertikal prujinaga osilgan bo'lsin. Yuk biroz pastga tortilib, keyin qo'yib yuborilganda prujina massasini havo qarshiligini hisobga olmagan holda yukning harakat qonuni va tenglamasini oliy matematikaning yuqori tartibli o'zgarmas koeffitsientli chiziqli differentsial tenglamalar bo'limidan foydalanib topamiz [1].

Buning uchun, OX o'qni yuk osilgan nuqta orqali pastga rasmda ko'rsatilganidek yo'naltiramiz. Koordinatalar boshi O nuqtani yuk muvozanatda bo'lgan holatda, ya'ni yukning og'irligi prujinaning reaksiya kuchi bilan muvozanatlashgan nuqtada olamiz.

Agar λ – prujinaning ayni paytdagi uzayishi, λ_{cr} esa statik uzayish, ya'ni cho'zilmagan prujina oxiridan muvozanat holatigacha bo'lgan masofa. U holda $\lambda = \lambda_{cr} + x$ yoki $\lambda - \lambda_{cr} = x$ (1) bo'ladi.

Endi bu harakatning differentsial tenglamasini Nyutonning ikkinchi qonunidan

$$F = ma \quad (2)$$

foydalanib topamiz. Bu yerda $m = \frac{F}{a}$ – yuk massasi, a – harakat tezlanishi va F - yukka qo'yilgan kuchlarning teng ta'sir etuvchisidan iborat. Bu holda teng ta'sir etuvchi kuch prujinaning taranglik kuchi va og'irlik kuchlari yig'indisidan iborat bo'ladi.

Guk qonuniga ko'ra prujinaning taranglik kuchi uning uzayishiga to'g'ri proporsional bo'lib $c\lambda$ – ga teng bo'ladi. Bu yerda c – o'zgarmas sonidan iborat bo'lib, o'zgarmas proporsionallik koeffitsienti deyiladi va uni prujinaning bikrligi deb ham ataymiz. Shularni

hisobga olib, harakatning ikkinchi tartibli differentsial tenglamasi quyidagi tenglamadan iborat bo'ladi:

$$m \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = -c\lambda + P \quad (3)$$

Muvozanat holatida prujinaning taranglik kuchi og'irlik kuchi bilan muvozanatlashgani uchun

$$P = c\lambda_{cT} \quad (4)$$

bo'lishini bilgan holda, (3) differentsial tenglamaga R ning ifodasini qo'yib va $\lambda - \lambda_{cT}$ -ushbu hadni ni x bilan belgilab, tenglamani ushbu

$$m \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = -c\lambda + c\lambda_{cT}, \quad m \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = -c(\lambda - \lambda_{cT}), \quad \lambda - \lambda_{cT} = x \quad \text{bolgani uchun} \quad m \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = -cx$$

ko'rinishga keltiramiz. Bundan $\frac{c}{m}$ ni k^2 - orqali belgilab,

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + k^2x = 0 \quad (5)$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Bu tenglamaga yukning erkin tebranishlari tenglamasi deb atalgan tebranishni ifodalaydi. Unga garmonik ostsilyatorning tenglamasi deyiladi. Matematikada bu koeffitsientlar o'zgarmas bo'lgan ikkinchi tartibli chiziqli bir jinsli differentsial tenglama deyiladi. Bu tenglamaning yechimini topish uchun uning xarakteristik tenglamasi deb ataluvchi

$$r^2 + k^2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

tenglama tuziladi va uning yechimi $r = \pm ik$ ildizlarga ega bo'lib, unga ya'ni (5) ga tegishli bo'lgan umumiy yechim:

$$x = c_1 \cos kt + c_2 \sin kt \quad (7) \text{ kabi topiladi.}$$

Echimni fizikaviy ma'nosini aniqlash uchun yangi ixtiyoriy o'zgarmas kiritib, uni boshqacharoq shaklga keltiramiz. (7) ni $\sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2}$ ga ko'paytirib va bo'lib quyidagi tenglamani hosil qilamiz:

$$x = \sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2} \left(\frac{c_1}{\sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2}} \cos kx + \frac{c_2}{\sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2}} \sin kt \right)$$

Agar $\sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2} = A$, $\frac{c_1}{\sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2}} = \sin \alpha$, $\frac{c_2}{\sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2}} = \cos \alpha$ deb belgilash kiritsak u holda yechim

$$x = A \sin(kt + \alpha) \quad (8)$$

ko'rinishga keladi. Bundan xulosa qilib, yuk muvozanat holati atrofida garmonik tebranishini aniqladik.

A – kattalikka tebranishning amplitudasi,, $kt + \alpha$ argument esa tebranish fazasi deyiladi.. Fazaning $t = 0$ dagi qiymati, ya'ni α kattalik tebranishning boshlang'ich fazasi deyiladi. $k =$

Tebranishning $T = \frac{2\pi}{k} = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{c}}$ davri va k chastota faqat

$c = \frac{P}{\lambda_{cT}} = \frac{mg}{\lambda_{cT}}$ bo'lgani sababli davr uchun $T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{cT}}{g}}$ formulani ham hosil qilish mumkin

bo'ladi.

Yukning harakat tezligining yechimini t bo'yicha differentsiallash orqali topamiz:

$$v = \frac{dx}{dt} = Ak \cos(kt + \alpha)$$

Amplituda va boshlang'ich fazani aniqlash uchun boshlang'ich shartlar berilgan bo'lishi kerak. Aytaylik, boshlang'ich $t=0$ momentda yukning holati $x = x_0$ va tezligi $\vartheta = \vartheta_0$ bo'lsin. U holda $x_0 = A \sin \alpha$, $\vartheta_0 = A k \cos \alpha$, bu yerda

$$A = \sqrt{x_0^2 + \frac{\vartheta_0^2}{k^2}}, \quad \alpha = \arctg \frac{kx_0}{\vartheta_0} \text{ bo'ladi...}$$

Amplituda va boshlang'ich faza formulalaridan ko'rinadiki, ular xususiy tebranishlar chastotasi va davridan farqli, sistemaning boshlang'ich holatiga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Boshlang'ich tezlik bo'lmaganda $\vartheta_0 = 0$ amplituda $A = x_0$, boshlang'ich faza esa $\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2}$ bo'lib, $x = x_0 \sin \left(kt + \frac{\pi}{2} \right)$ ёки $x = x_0 \cos kt$ bo'ladi.

Agar sonli ma'lumotlar berilgan bo'lsa, $P = 2 \text{ H}$, $l = 40 \text{ cm}$, $\lambda_{CT} = 4 \text{ sm}$, shu bilan birga yuk $x = 2 \text{ cm}$ ga tortilib, boshlang'ich tezliksiz ($\vartheta_0 = 0$) qo'yib yuborilgan bo'lsa, u holda harakat qonuni (8) formulaga asosan

$$x = A \sin(kt + \alpha)$$

ko'rinishda aniqlanadi. Bu yerda $k = \sqrt{\frac{cg}{P}}$ частота $P = c \lambda_{CT}$ munosabat orqali aniqlanadi. $c = \frac{1}{2}$ bo'lsa, $k = \sqrt{\frac{g}{2}}$, $A = \sqrt{x_0^2 + \frac{\vartheta_0^2}{k^2}} = 2$, $\alpha = \operatorname{arctg} \left(\frac{kx_0}{\vartheta_0} \right) = \frac{\pi}{2}$ бўлиб $x = 2 \cos \frac{t}{2} \sqrt{g}$ ni hosil qilamiz.

Yukning tebranish davrini $T = \frac{2\pi}{k} = \frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{g}} \approx 0,4 \text{ sek}$. Eng katta cho'zish $\lambda_{max} = \lambda_{CT} + A = 6 \text{ sm}$. Prujinaning eng katta taranglik kuchi $F_{max} = c \lambda_{max} = 3 \text{ H}$ bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda garmonik tebranishlarning harakat qonunlarini “Oliy matematika”, differensial tenglamalar nazariyasi orqali aniqlash va topish mumkin ekan.

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